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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Marfan syndrome (MFS) is a systemic, autosomal dominant connective tissue disorder. It typically presents with features such as tall stature, long limbs, scoliosis, lens dislocation, and aortic root dilatation. The prevalence of Marfan syndrome is estimated to be approximately 1 in 5,000 to 1 in 10,000 live births. About 75% of cases are familial, while 25% arise from de novo mutations (Judge & Dietz, 2005). The most commonly implicated gene in Marfan syndrome is *FBN1* (*Fibrillin-1*). Mutations in *FBN1* disrupt microfibril integrity and lead to increased TGF- β activity, resulting in weakened connective tissue (Ramirez & Sakai, 2010). More than 3,000 different *FBN1* mutations have been reported in the literature, with common pathogenic variants including c.7558C>T (p.Arg2520Cys), c.5788G>A (p.Cys1930Tyr), and c.1453C>T (p.Arg485Cys) (Comeglio et al., 2002; Faivre et al., 2007; Loeys et al., 2010). The most widely used diagnostic system for Marfan syndrome is the revised Ghent nosology (Ghent-2 criteria), which assigns points based on clinical findings across organ systems. A systemic score of ≥ 7 is considered the diagnostic cutoff (Loeys et al., 2010).

Materials and Methods: Blood samples were collected in EDTA tubes from 10 patients who scored ≥ 7 points. The entire coding region of the *FBN1* gene was sequenced using next-generation sequencing (NGS).

Results:

Patient 1: Male patient with tall stature, aortic root dilatation, and myopia. Family history revealed similar findings in the father. Ghent-2 score > 7 . Family testing could not be performed. *FBN1*: c.6680C>T, p.Ser2227Leu

Patient 2: Female patient with tall, marfanoid appearance and myopia. Her father presented with a similar phenotype and had a history of spontaneous pneumothorax. Ghent-2 score > 7 . *FBN1*: c.288del, p.Arg96Serfs*12).

Patient 3: Male patient with tall stature and aortic root dilatation. No relevant family history. *FBN1*: c.5003_5004delinsCT, p.Ile1668Ala

Conclusion: Among 70 patients examined in our outpatient clinic with suspicion of Marfan syndrome, 3 of the 10 patients who underwent genetic testing were found to carry mutations consistent with their clinical presentation. A correlation between genotype and phenotype was achieved. To our knowledge, this is the first study conducted in Ordu Province focusing on the genetic background of Marfan syndrome. Moreover, the variants identified in our study have not been previously reported in the literature, making this study significant for contributing three novel mutations to the spectrum of *FBN1* mutations associated with Marfan syndrome.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Marfan syndrome, FBN1 gene, genetic testing

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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